

JURISPRUDENCE

INTERNATIONAL LEGAL REGULATION OF POSSIBLE RESTRICTIONS ON HUMAN RIGHTS TO INFORMATION

Nugmanov N.

DSc, Professor

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14236905>

Abstract

This article examines the issues of regulation at the international and national levels of the right to allow legitimate restrictions on human rights to information based on considerations of private, personal or national security. The purpose of this article is to study the issues of international legal regulation of possible restrictions on human rights to freedom of information. It is substantiated that each state is obliged to ensure human rights to information and freedom of speech within the framework of its authority and to the extent specified in international agreements, among which the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights occupies a special place.

Keywords: international law, information sphere, international information law, human rights to information.

Human rights to freedom of information are implemented on the basis of constitutional and national law, since international legal treaties do not directly regulate the legal status of individuals. The main object of such national legal relations is the right to information, and the subjects are any individuals or legal entities. At the same time, each state is obliged to ensure human rights to information and freedom of speech within the framework of its authority and to the extent specified in international agreements, among which the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights occupies a special place (1).

Article 19 of this document states that everyone has the right to freely hold opinions and express opinions; this right includes freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas of all kinds, regardless of frontiers, either orally, in writing, in print or in the form of art, or through any other means of one's choice. The exercise of rights in accordance with paragraph 2 of Article 19 shall be subject to certain restrictions that are established by law and are necessary: a) to respect the rights and reputations of others; b) to protect national security, public order, health and morals of the population". (2) Paragraph 1 of Article 19 refers to the human right to protect a person's privacy from outside interference, paragraphs 2 and 3 directly refer to a person's information rights and obligations. It should be noted that restrictions on freedom of information may only be established by law. It should be noted that Article 19 is technologically quite neutral, in addition to its interactive emphasis. It does not refer to old media or new media, but rather to "all media and regardless of borders" (3).

According to Article 20 of the Covenant, any propaganda for war is prohibited by international law; any advocacy of national, racial or religious hatred that constitutes incitement to discrimination, hostility or violence must be prohibited by law (4). This means that the ban on the dissemination of these types of information must be enshrined in law.

International agreements of a regional nature also have similar provisions on human rights in the field of information. For example, Article 10 of the Convention

for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, adopted by the Council of Europe in 1950, proclaims the human right to freedom of expression, to "receive and impart information and ideas without interference by public authority and regardless of frontiers" (5). The Convention (paragraph 2 of Article 10) provides for the possibility of restrictions on the right to information related to ensuring national security, territorial integrity or public order, the prevention of disorder or crime, the protection of health or morals, the protection of the reputation or rights of others, preventing the publication of information received in confidence, or maintaining the authority or impartiality of the judiciary (6).

In accordance with Article 13 of the American Convention on Human Rights of 1969, states parties are obliged to guarantee the freedom to "seek, receive and impart information and ideas", regardless of frontiers and in any form (7). This Convention prohibits any form of state censorship, except for the need to restrict access to information for the protection of the morals of children and adolescents (paragraph 4). Restrictions regarding the use of freedom of information are similar to the restrictions specified in Articles 19 and 20 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966 (8). In accordance with Article 14 of the Convention provides for the right to refute offensive or distorted information using the same medium and under the conditions established by law.

It is important to emphasize here that since the basis of the Concept of Human Rights is the provision according to which the main subject of the right to freedom of speech and information is the individual, responsibility for the dissemination of illegal information by citizens lies with the state. This means that balancing the use of freedom of information by a person is one of the tasks of state regulation.

Subsequently, the human right to freedom of information was recorded in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966, which is the basic international legal agreement in the field of ensuring human information rights. In accordance with the provisions of Article 19 of the Covenant, the human right

to freely "seek, receive and impart all kinds of information and ideas regardless of state borders" is established.

Unlike the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, which has dispositive nature, the Covenant is imperative, therefore, when formulating human rights to information, it is necessary to rely on the provisions of Articles 19 and 20 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (9). It should be noted that such countries as the United States, Belgium, Switzerland, etc. have not ratified the Covenant. And the Netherlands, Sweden, Denmark, and Finland made reservations regarding the rights to information in relation to the provisions of Articles 19 and 20 of the Covenant (10). At the same time, all countries regulate the procedure for disseminating and the content of information within their jurisdiction to varying degrees. It follows from this that the concept of unlimited human information rights contained in international agreements is not always ensured at the national level.

In the states of the Council of Europe, the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, adopted by the European Community on November 4, 1950, is in force and has much greater legal significance (11). In Art. 10 The Convention establishes the human right to "receive and impart information and ideas without interference from public authorities and regardless of frontiers" (12). However, it does not include the right to seek information. It turns out that there is a restriction on the active and effective form of realizing the information need.

In addition, it should be noted that in addition to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, European legislation also contains other legal acts regulating various relations in the sphere of access of individuals and society to information. One of the important such legal documents is the new version of the Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe R (81) 19 to the member states of the Council of Europe - "On access to official information held by public authorities", adopted on February 21, 2002 (13). This legal act was the result of the work of the international group of experts on access to official information (DHSAC) under the Organizing Committee on Human Rights of the Council of Europe and now its new name is Recommendation No. R (2002) 2 "On access to official documents". Also, the Recommendation of the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe R (94) 13 "On measures to ensure transparency of the media" of 22 November 1994 is very significant for the formation and development of the constitutional institution of freedom of the media (14). The first paragraph of the document "Public access to information about the media" determines that "the public should have the opportunity to access on a fair and impartial basis to certain basic information about the media". This document designates the legal regime of the so-called transparency of electronic media, since it provides an opportunity to form an opinion in relation to the disseminated information depending on who is the owner of a particular media outlet.

Undoubtedly, it is also necessary to note such an important legal document regulating relations in the field of public access to information is the Council of Europe Convention on Access to Official Documents adopted in Tromsø (Norway) on 18 June 2009 (15). This legal act is the first binding international treaty that has secured the universal right of access to official documents held by the authorities. This agreement sets minimum rules for the timely and fair processing of requests for official documents, including the obligation of states to guarantee the possibility of effective and independent appeal against refusals. According to this agreement, all official documents must be public, and access to them can only be restricted to protect other rights and legitimate interests. It should be noted that the Council of Europe Convention on Access to Official Documents entered into force on 1 December 2020 with respect to Ukraine, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Estonia, Finland, Hungary, Lithuania, Montenegro, Norway, the Republic of Moldova and Sweden. In our opinion, this document is one of the advanced international agreements ensuring transparency of public authorities on a mandatory and legal basis.

Considering the growing role of the environmental protection sphere and at the same time the key role of ensuring access to information in the environmental protection sphere, in our opinion it is necessary to note the UN Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters adopted in Aarhus (Denmark) on June 25, 1998 (Aarhus Convention) (16), which contains provisions regarding the rights of access to information in the environmental sphere and in turn supplements the Tromsø Convention of 2009.

Based on the above, we believe that the legal regulation of relations in the field of ensuring human information rights is an important and constantly updated element of the subject of legal regulation of international information law. Probably, the further development of national legal relations to ensure information freedom and rights will increasingly develop under the direct and sensitive influence of international legal norms in the field of ensuring human information rights. In our opinion, it is reasonable to assert that in the conditions of development of the modern information society and global information space, namely in the conditions of increasing role of information, knowledge and information technologies in the life of society, the formation of a unified or global international information and legal status of a person is proceeding in an evolutionary way.

At the same time, there are legitimate conditions for limiting the information rights and freedoms of a person, since the rights and freedoms of a person to information have never had an absolute character anywhere. Undoubtedly, these restrictions on working with information correspond to the restrictions contained in international normative legal acts. For example, in accordance with Article 10 of the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, adopted in Rome on 4 November 1950, freedom of information and expression must have certain restrictions associated with "the formalities, conditions,

restrictions or penalties which are prescribed by law and which are necessary in a democratic society in the interests of national security, territorial integrity or public safety, for the prevention of disorder or crime, for the protection of health or morals, for the protection of the reputation or rights of others, for preventing the disclosure of information received in confidence, or for maintaining the authority and impartiality of the judiciary" (17).

There are numerous decisions of the European Court of Human Rights related to the application of Article 10 of the European Convention and concerning the issue of restrictions on information rights and freedoms. Based on many years of experience, the European Court has formed certain legal mechanisms for assessing the legality of state actions to restrict information rights and freedoms. This assessment mechanism is based on such criteria as whether the authorities' actions were based on the law, whether they correspond to the objectives of the restrictions (provided for in paragraph 2 of Article 10) and to what extent such restrictions were necessary.

Thus, it can be noted that both international and national law allow legitimate restrictions of human rights to information based on considerations of private, personal or national security and for a number of other reasons. This circumstance is confirmed not only by international and national legal acts, but also by a number of the above-mentioned decisions of European and other international judicial institutions and bodies.

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